

MEAN EDGE CORDIAL LABELING OF WHEEL RELATED GRAPHS

Joshua Wilson K¹ and Veninstine Vivik J²

Research Scholar, Karunya Institute of Technology and Sciences, Coimbatore - 641114, India.¹

Assistant Professor, Karunya Institute of Technology and Sciences, Coimbatore - 641114, India.²

Email: joshuawilson1142@gmail.com¹, vivikjose@gmail.com²

ABSTRACT

Graph labeling involves assigning values to the vertices and edges of a graph. Mean edge cordial labeling is a recently introduced binary edge labeling scheme in which vertex labels are obtained from the mean of the labels on incident edges, resulting in a balanced distribution that satisfies cordial conditions. In this paper, we investigate the existence of this labeling for several wheel-based graph structures, namely Wheel graphs, Helm graphs, Closed Helm graphs, Gear graphs, and Web graphs. For each class, constructive labeling patterns are developed and verified to ensure that both the induced vertex labeling and the edge labeling satisfy the required cordial properties.

Keywords: Graph Labeling, Cordial Labeling, Mean Edge Cordial Labeling, Wheel Structured graphs.

MSC Classification: 05C78.

INTRODUCTION

Graph labeling is an assignment of integers to vertices or edges or both vertices and edges of the graph subject to certain conditions. The origin of graph labeling can be attributed to Rosa [1] and Gallian [4]. Cordial labelling of graphs was introduced by Cahit [3] as a weakened version of graceful labeling and harmonious labeling. Graph labeling is a strong communication between number theory and structure of graphs. Mean Edge cordial labeling (\mathcal{MECL}) is a new concept in graph theory that involves labeling in a specific way that edges are labeled first and vertices are assigned labels based on the value of the labeled edges incident with that vertex. The concept of \mathcal{MECL} focuses on ensuring that the distribution of label is cordial or balanced in such a way that it can be applied to the both vertices and edges of the graph. In this paper, we establish the existence of \mathcal{MECL} for Wheel, Helm, Closed Helm Gear, and Web graph by constructing appropriate edge labeling patterns and verifying the required cordial conditions.

PRELIMINARIES

This section consists of some predefined definitions that is necessary in proving the upcoming results. It is to be noted that all the graphs considered in this paper are connected and undirected. $V(G) = \{v_i/i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$, $E(G) = \{e_i/i = 1, 2, \dots, m\}$ and $f: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ denotes the vertex set, edge set and the edge labeling function of the graph G respectively. We examine binary edge assignments on a simple graph G , under which the vertices inherit their states through local averaging of incident edge values. A vertex is declared dominant whenever the balance of its incident edges does not fall below the midpoint threshold; otherwise, it assumes the complementary state. When this induced propagation preserves near equilibrium between the two states across both edges and vertices that is, their respective counts differ by at most 1, the graph is regarded as exhibiting a mean edge cordial configuration [7].

Definition 1. A cycle C_n is a closed path in which all vertices are distinct except the initial and terminal vertices, that is a sequence of vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n, v_1$ with $n \geq 3$, in which all vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n are distinct and each v_i is adjacent to v_{i+1} and v_n is adjacent to v_1 .

Definition 2. A wheel graph W_n is defined as the join $K_1 + C_n$. The vertex corresponding to K_1 is called apex, the vertices corresponding to the cycle are called rim vertices and the edges of C_n are called rim edges.

Definition 3. The gear graph G_n is obtained from the wheel W_n by subdividing each of its rim edge.

Definition 4. The helm graph H_n is obtained from W_n by attaching a pendant edge to each rim vertex.

Definition 5. The closed helm graph CH_n is obtained from a helm H_n by joining each pendant vertex to form a cycle.

Definition 6. The web graph Wb_n is obtained by joining the pendant vertices of a helm H_n to form a cycle and then adding a pendant edge to each vertex of outer cycle.

RESULTS

Theorem 1: The Wheel graph W_n is mean edge cordial graph for $n \geq 3$.

Proof:

Let v_0 be the apex vertex and v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the vertices, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n be the rim edges and e'_1, e'_2, \dots, e'_n be the spoke edges of the W_n .

define a mapping $f: E(W_n) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ we consider following two cases.

Case 1: When n is odd.

$$\begin{aligned} f(e_i) &= 1; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2} \\ f(e_i) &= 0; \text{ otherwise} \\ f(e'_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2} \\ f(e'_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: When n is even.

$$\begin{aligned} f(e_i) &= 1; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1 \\ f(e_i) &= 0; \text{ otherwise} \\ f(e'_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1 \\ f(e'_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

In both the cases the defined labeling patterns are

$$\begin{aligned} v_f(0) &= v_f(1) = \frac{n+1}{2}; \text{ when } n \text{ is odd} \\ v_f(0) &= v_f(1) - 1 = \frac{n}{2}; \text{ when } n \text{ is even} \\ e_f(0) &= e_f(1) = n \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have $|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \leq 1$.

Hence the Wheel graph is a mean edge cordial graph for $n \geq 3$.

The illustration of Wheel graphs W_5 and W_6 are shown in Figures 1.1 and 1.2

Figure 1.1. W_5 (n is odd)

Figure 1.2. W_6 (n is even)

Theorem 2: The Gear graph G_n is mean edge cordial graph for $n \geq 3$.

Proof:

Let v_0 be the apex vertex and v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the vertices on the rim and u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n be the vertices subdividing it. Let e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n be the spoke edges and $e'_1, e'_2, \dots, e'_{2n}$ be the rim edges of the Gear G_n .

define a mapping $f: E(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ we consider following two cases.

Case 1: When n is odd.

$$f(e_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$$

$$f(e_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

$$f(e'_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(e'_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

Case 2: When n is even.

$$f(e_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1$$

$$f(e_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

$$f(e'_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$$

$$f(e'_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

In both the cases the defined labeling patterns are

$$v_f(0) = v_f(1) - 1 = n$$

$$e_f(0) + 1 = e_f(1) = \frac{3n+1}{2}; \text{ when } n \text{ is odd}$$

$$e_f(0) = e_f(1) = \frac{3n}{2}; \text{ when } n \text{ is even}$$

Thus, we have $|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \leq 1$.

Hence the Gear graph is a mean edge cordial graph for $n \geq 3$.

The illustration of Gear graphs G_7 and G_8 are shown in Figures 2.1 and 2.2

Figure 2.1 G_7 (n is odd)

Figure 2.2 G_8 (n is even)

Theorem 3: The Helm graph H_n is mean edge cordial graph for $n \geq 3$.

Proof:

Let v_0 be the apex vertex and v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the vertices and e'_1, e'_2, \dots, e'_n be the edges on the rim. Let e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n be the spoke edges. Let $e^a_1, e^a_2, \dots, e^a_n$ be the pendant edges connecting the pendant vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n of the Helm H_n . define a mapping $f: E(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ we consider following two cases.

Case 1: When n is odd.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(e_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2} \\
 f(e_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e'_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2} \\
 f(e'_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e^a_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\
 f(e^a_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise}
 \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: When n is even.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(e_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1 \\
 f(e_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e'_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\
 f(e'_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e^a_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} - 1 \\
 f(e^a_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise}
 \end{aligned}$$

In both the cases the defined labeling patterns are

$$\text{i) } \text{odd} = \begin{cases} v_f(0) - 1 = v_f(1) = n \\ e_f(0) = e_f(1) + 1 = \frac{3n+1}{2} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{ii) } \text{even} = \begin{cases} v_f(0) = v_f(1) - 1 = n \\ e_f(0) = e_f(1) = \frac{3n}{2} \end{cases}$$

Thus, we have $|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \leq 1$.

Hence the Helm graph is a mean edge cordial graph for $n \geq 3$.

The illustration of Helm graphs H_5 and H_6 are shown in Figures 3.1 and 3.2

Figure 3.1. H_5 (n is odd)

Figure 3.2 H_6 (n is even)

Theorem 4: The Closed Helm graph CH_n is mean edge cordial graph for $n \geq 3$.

Proof:

Let v_0 be the apex vertex, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the vertices and e'_1, e'_2, \dots, e'_n be the edges of the inner circle. Let e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n be the spoke edges. Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n be vertices, $e^a_1, e^a_2, \dots, e^a_n$ be the edges of the outer circle and $e^a_1, e^a_2, \dots, e^a_n$ be the edges connecting outer circle vertices to the inner circle rim vertices of the closed helm CH_n .

define a mapping $f: E(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ we consider following two cases.

Case 1: When n is odd.

$$f(e_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2}$$

$$f(e_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

$$f(e'_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2}$$

$$f(e'_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

$$f(e^a_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$$

$$f(e^a_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

$$f(e^{a'}_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$$

$$f(e^{a'}_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

Case 2: When n is even.

$$f(e_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1$$

$$f(e_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

$$f(e'_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2}$$

$$f(e'_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

$$f(e^a_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} - 1$$

$$f(e^a_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

$$f(e^{a'}_i) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2}$$

$$f(e^{a'}_i) = 1; \text{ otherwise}$$

The defined labeling patterns are

$$v_f(0) - 1 = v_f(1) = n$$

$$e_f(0) = e_f(1) = 2n$$

Thus, we have $|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \leq 1$.

Hence the Closed Helm graph is a mean edge cordial graph for $n \geq 3$.

The illustration of Closed Helm graphs CH_5 and CH_6 are shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2

Figure 4.1 CH_5 (n is even)

Figure 4.2 CH_6 (n is even)

Theorem 5 The Web Wb_n is mean edge cordial graph for $n \geq 3$.

Proof:

Let v_0 be the apex vertex, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the vertices and e'_1, e'_2, \dots, e'_n be the edges of the inner circle. Let e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n be the spoke edges. Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n be vertices, $e^{a'}_1, e^{a'}_2, \dots, e^{a'}_n$ be the edges of the outer circle and $e^a_1, e^a_2, \dots, e^a_n$ be the edges connecting outer circle vertices to the inner circle rim vertices. Let $e^b_1, e^b_2, \dots, e^b_n$ be the pendant edges in the outer circle vertices of the Web Wb_n .

define a mapping $f: E(Wb_n) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ we consider following two cases.

Case 1: When n is odd.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(e_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2} \\
 f(e_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e'_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2} \\
 f(e'_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e^a_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2} \\
 f(e^a_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e^{a'}_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\
 f(e^{a'}_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e^b_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\
 f(e^b_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise}
 \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: When n is even.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(e_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1 \\
 f(e_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e'_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} - 1 \\
 f(e'_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e^a_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\
 f(e^a_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e^{a'}_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\
 f(e^{a'}_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise} \\
 f(e^b_i) &= 0; 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\
 f(e^b_i) &= 1; \text{ otherwise}
 \end{aligned}$$

In both the cases the defined labeling patterns are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{iii)} \quad \text{odd} &= \begin{cases} v_f(0) = v_f(1) = \frac{3n+1}{2} \\ e_f(0) = e_f(1) - 1 = \frac{5n+1}{2} \end{cases} \\
 \text{iv)} \quad \text{even} &= \begin{cases} v_f(0) - 1 = v_f(1) = \frac{3n}{2} \\ e_f(0) = e_f(1) = \frac{5n}{2} \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have $|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \leq 1$.

Hence the Web graph is a mean edge cordial graph for $n \geq 4$.

The illustration of Web graphs Wb_5 and Wb_6 are shown in Figures 5.1 and 5.2

Figure 5.1 Wb_5 (n is odd)

Figure 5.2 Wb_6 (n is even)

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we study the \mathcal{MECL} of some wheel structured graphs such as Wheel, Gear, Helm, Closed helm and web graph. Appropriate binary edge labeling obtained from the mean of incident edges was shown to satisfy the cordial conditions for these structures. Hence, the considered wheel family graphs admit \mathcal{MECL} under defined labeling scheme. Further, the proposed labeling approach can be extended to other wheel structured graphs in future studies.

REFERENCES

1. Alex Rosa, On certain valuations of the vertices of a graph, Theory of Graphs, Internat. Symposium, Rome, July 1966 (Gordon and Breach, New York) (1967), 349–355.
2. Bondy. J. A and Murty. U. S. R., “Graph Theory with Applications,” American Elsevier, New York, 1976.
3. Cahit, I, “Cordial Graphs: A Weaker Version of Graceful and Harmonious Graphs,” Ars Combinatorial, Vol. 23, 1987, pp. 201-207.
4. Gallian, J. A. (2022). A dynamic survey of graph labeling. Electronic Journal of combinatorics, 6(25), 4-623.
5. J. Gross and J. Yellen, Handbook of graph theory, CRC Press (2004).
6. Joshua Wilson, K., & Veninstine Vivik, J. (2026). Mean edge cordial labeling of flower family graphs. *Indian Journal of Natural Sciences*, 17(95), 1–9.
7. Joshua Wilson, K., & Veninstine Vivik, J. (2025). Mean edge cordial labeling of path structured graphs with applications. *Panamerican Mathematical Journal*, 35(4s), 1894–1910. <https://doi.org/10.52783/pmj.v35.i4s.6753>
8. Joshua Wilson K, Veninstine Vivik J, “Modeling Biometric Sensor Arrays Through Mean Edge Cordial Labeling of Grid Graphs”. (Communicated)

9. Vaidya, S. K., & Barasara, C. M. (2012). Edge product cordial labeling of graphs. *J. Math. Comput. Sci.*, 2(5), 1436-1450.
10. Vaidya, S. K., & Shah, N. H. (2013). Prime cordial labeling of some wheel related graphs. *Malaya Journal of Matematik*, 4(1), 148-156.
11. Vaidya, S. K., & Kanani, K. K. (2010). Some cycle related product cordial graphs. *Int. J. of Algorithms, Comp. and Math*, 3(1), 109-116.
12. Vivik, J. V., & Xavier, P. (2021, December). Energy of 2-Corona of Graphs. In *Mathematical Modeling, Computational Intelligence Techniques and Renewable Energy: Proceedings of the Second International Conference, MMCITRE 2021*, pp. 67-75.